

GENREAL FEATURES OF MODERN ART

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¹ UzDSMI, "Variety and mass performances

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Because of the introduction of modern technologies into our lives, people's consciousness, worldview, aesthetic tastes in art are changing in a similar way. This of course also has an impact on the art of laughter. Along with modern technologies, various comedy genres and styles are entering our variety. Adapting their scientific foundations to our mentality with deep study, applying their achievements in practice will serve as an important factor for the development of comedy. Examples of genres that are widely used in the art of comedy today are: parody, miniature theater, stand up, sketch, reprise, prank.

The theater of miniatures is a compact work, consisting of a one-act play, an interlude, a parable, a monologue, a comedy, a comedy, etc., and is sometimes subordinated to a common plot. Shortcomings in life, funny events, everyday problems and current issues are

ABSTRACT

The article examines the stages of development of traditional art according to interests, methods of performance, types. When covering the topic, the teacher relied on the creative activity of enthusiasts.

expressed through satire and humor. The modern European-style miniature theater appeared in France in the second half of the 19th century. In Uzbekistan, the roots of this genre of play go back to ancient comedy theater. The national style miniature theater has developed in accordance with the spirit of the time, mastering many forms of art of clowning, hobby. In 1962, the Television Miniature Theater was established under the Yoshlik studio of the Uzbek Television. Interesting groups such as "Comedy Show" are widely used on stage.

The parody is one of the genres of literature, theater, music and pop, comedy, comedy and humor, meaning "contradictory song" from Greek to Uzbek. A specific style of action is also a conscious imitation aimed at approaching a style, direction, genre, or speech in a particular pattern with humor, satire, and humor. A

funny work created by imitating the work of an artist or the style of an individual work.

Some events in socio-political, domestic life can also be the subject of parody. Parody is also a peculiar direction of comedy art, satire. A parody is often exaggerated, in which the form and content of the event being portrayed are in conflict with each other.

Parodies called muqallids have played an important role in the repertoire of the Uzbek traditional theater. Most of the clowns and amateurs showed skill in this. In the first half of the twentieth century, parodies of Yusufjon Qiziq, Akhunjon Qiziq, Aka Bukhara, Berdiyov Mashara, Safar Mashara and others were popular. Haji Tam-tam (Hojikurban Hamidov) was a master of music and parody of singers.

Today, the number of artists and creative groups working in this genre is growing significantly. Bands such as "Imitation Show", "Aristocrats", "Design" widely use parody in their concert programs. The Actor Show project, which has been aired on Zo'r TV since 2019, is also discovering many young parody artists.

The stand-up genre is also a form of comedy art, where the soloist has the art of telling jokes in front of a live audience and interacting directly with them. Often special comedy clubs are organized for the stands. Creators in this genre are called stand-up comics, stand-up actors, comics, or stand-up comics. Stand-up comedy material usually consists of stories and jokes.

Stand-ups are held in comedy clubs, bars, leisure centers and other venues intended

for performances in front of an audience. In addition to live performances, the stand-up will be distributed commercially via CD, DVD, television and the Internet.

Today, Ozod Shukrulloev, Indira Miftakhova, Islam Karimov and many other young performers are contributing to the development of Uzbek stand-up programs on Zo'r TV and Milliy TV channels. In addition, a number of performances in the repertoires of the late Uzbek amateurs Muhiddin Darvesh, Rustam Hamrokulov, Hojiboy Tadjibayev, Obid Asomov and Mirzabek Holmedov, Avaz Ohun, who are still active, correspond to several types of stand-up in terms of form and content.

Sketch is a short funny situation involving a small number of characters (usually two, rarely three). This type of art, derived from folk interludes, originated in the 16th century and is most common on the western stage. With the development of television, the genre called "sketch show" or "sketch comedy" became widespread. This is a TV show with several jokes that are not connected to each other.

Similar programs on Russian television: "Gentleman's show", "Gorodok", "6 shots", "Our Russia", "Give youth!", "One man for all", "Unreal story", "HB", "Sashatanya", jokes for children and adults "Eralash" and others.

This type of program is also widespread on Uzbek television. Examples include Sketch Show, Grapes, Boomerang, and Qatra Handa. Stage sketches are widely used in the concert repertoire of creative teams such as "Million", "Design", "Bravo", "Maximum", formed on the basis of the game "Cheerful and clever".

REPRIZE (French repris repetition, repetition) - 1) in circus and pop - a comic literary or pantomime number (sometimes a joke; anecdote). In circus art, the term Repriza has been used since the first half of the 19th century. Uzbek clowns and amateurs, as well as circus clowns (K. Zarifov, A. Yusupov, N. Nurmatov, E. Parpiev, O. Khakimov, G. Zastavnikov, P. Borovikov) used reprisals effectively.

In conclusion, it is necessary to say that in order to create modern comedy that can fully meet the needs of today's audience, the performer, along with talent, requires intellectual potential, deep socio-political knowledge. One of the most important tools in educating mature artists in the field of comedy is the creation of a textbook that combines the knowledge of the school of national interest and the scientific basis of modern world comedy.

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